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Religious Tolerance and Social Harmony in the Mughal Era: A Historical Study

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Abstract

This research paper analyzes the religious policies of the Mughal rulers, highlighting their efforts to unify followers of various faiths and foster religious tolerance. Through their inclusive approach, the Mughals contributed to the development of a syncretic culture in India, commonly known as the Ganga-Jamuni Tehzeeb. The contribution of Emperor Akbar in this regard is particularly noteworthy. Policies such as Sulh-e-Kul (universal peace), royal patronage of Hindu temples, and the appointment of administrators without religious discrimination played a crucial role in promoting interfaith harmony. However, later colonial historians attempted to weaken this tradition to solidify British rule and exploit India economically. This research paper clarifies that the Mughal era laid the foundation for a shared cultural and historical heritage, which continues to shape India's secular ethos today.

Keywords Hindu-Muslim unity, Religious Tolerance and Social Harmony in the Mughal Era, Unity in diversity, Hindu-Muslim relationship in Medieval India.

Introduction

The mutual influence of India's diverse cultures and religions has given rise to a composite culture, known in North India as Ganga-Jamuni Tehzeeb. Since ancient times, various global cultures have settled in India, and Indian society has assimilated them, reinforcing its tradition of inclusivity. The immense diversity of Indian culture conveys the message of "unity in diversity" to the world. With the arrival of the Mughals, Indian culture absorbed them as well, making them an integral part of the subcontinent. The influence of Mughal culture led to the emergence of Hindustani culture, which profoundly impacted fields such as music, literature, architecture, craftsmanship, painting, and fine arts.* The Mughal rulers, by principle, did not follow a policy of religious discrimination and sought to separate religion from politics. Their policies were based on religious tolerance, influenced by the traditions of Genghis Khan and the Timurid dynasty. Genghis Khan implemented a legal code known as Yasa, referred to as Yasa-e-Chengezi. According to this law, a ruler was expected to treat all religions equally and not favor any particular sect or faith. As per Alauddin Ata Juvaini, Yasa-e-Chengezi mandated that the emperor should regard all religious sects equally, without discrimination. In adherence to this principle, Genghis Khan avoided religious bigotry and did not grant special preference to any particular sect. The rulers of the Timurid dynasty also followed a policy of religious tolerance, as evidenced by the absence of Shia persecution in Timurid territories.**

Objective of study

1. To highlight the principle of Indian secularism, which is an inherent characteristic of Indian culture, so that followers of different religions can view each other with love and respect.
2. To compile historical facts that promote love, non-violence, and harmony among the people living in the country.
3. To study Hindu-Muslim unity in Indian history.
4. To help understand and appreciate the shared cultural heritage of both communities.
5. Through historical evidence, this research aims to demonstrate how the tradition of coexistence and tolerance has played a crucial role in uniting different communities.

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Asian Resonance**Review of Literature**

1. Audrey Truschke (2017), *Aurangzeb: The Man and the Myth* – In this book, the author attempts to present a different perspective on Aurangzeb's reign and life. It challenges common perceptions and evaluates them based on historical facts.
2. Irfan Habib (2016), *Akbar and Contemporary India* – This book highlights the social, political, and cultural impacts of Emperor Akbar's reign. It particularly focuses on Akbar's religious tolerance and its influence on contemporary Indian society.
3. Mohammad Hifzur Rahman (2025), *An Overview of Mughal Grants to Promote Hindu Religion and Aurangzeb's Religious Policy* – In this work, the author provides a detailed account of land grants given by Mughal rulers to temples and religious institutions, with a special emphasis on Aurangzeb and his successors.
4. Athar Ali (1996), *The Evolution of the Perception of India: Akbar and Abul Fazl* – In this research paper, historian Athar Ali discusses Akbar's vision of India and his court historian Abul Fazl's portrayal of Indian society. The study highlights Abul Fazl's efforts to integrate diverse cultural elements, which contributed to the promotion of India's Ganga-Jamuni heritage.

Main Text

The founder of the Mughal Empire, Babur, had a liberal religious outlook and harbored no hostility toward Hindus. This is evident from his interactions with Hindu rulers. For instance, Haī Kakkār, the leader of the Kakkars, accepted Babur's authority, and as a result, Babur allowed him to retain his position. Similarly, Adam Kakkār participated in the Battle of Khanwa alongside Babur with his troops. Babur's religious tolerance is also reflected in his appreciation for painting, music, dance, and poetry—art forms that were often disapproved of by conservative Muslims of his time. Despite passing through Mathura multiple times, Babur never harmed its temples. He also documented the royal temples and idols in the Gwalior Fort but did not destroy them.* Babur's commitment to religious tolerance is further illustrated in the testament he left for his son, Humayun:- "In Hindustan, numerous religions coexist. We are grateful to Allah for granting us this empire. We must eliminate all forms of discrimination from our hearts and ensure that every community receives justice according to its traditions. To win the hearts of the people, avoid cow slaughter and include locals in the administration. Do not harm places of worship or temples within our empire. Adopt a system of governance that makes both the rulers and the people content. Islam spreads through good deeds, not through terror. Ignore the differences between Shias and Sunnis, as such divisions weaken Islam. Unite people of diverse customs so that no part of the empire becomes vulnerable."**

Humayun, like his father Babur, did not adopt a policy of religious intolerance against Hindus, nor did he declare any religious war against them. On the contrary, some Rajput rulers assisted him during difficult times. After the Battle of Chausa, Raja Veerman significantly helped Humayun. Later, when Humayun returned from Jodhpur and found himself without refuge, the ruler of Amarkot provided shelter to him and his family. This clearly indicates that Humayun followed a policy of cooperation with Hindus in India and, in return, received their support.***

In the 15th century, efforts to establish coordination between Hindu and Muslim communities were not only intellectual and cultural but also political. These efforts enhanced mutual understanding and cooperation between the two communities. When Akbar ascended the throne, he demonstrated his religious tolerance by abolishing the pilgrimage tax (Tirthakar) in 1563, which was levied on Hindus visiting sacred sites such as Mathura. This decision resulted in a significant loss of state revenue, amounting to millions. Prior to this, he had taken a crucial step by banning the enslavement of women and children from rebellious villages. Akbar also strengthened Hindu-Muslim ties by marrying Rajput princesses without forcing them to convert to Islam, allowing them full freedom to practice their faith. Notably, Birbal was permitted to carry idols of his deities while traveling with Akbar. Although Akbar was initially influenced by orthodox ulama, his policies reflected the liberal traditions of his predecessors. In 1564, Akbar abolished the jizya tax on non-Muslims. According to Abul Fazl, this decision was taken despite strong opposition from conservative Islamic scholars (ulama), with the argument that Hindus were also loyal subjects who diligently served the empire.****

In 1575, Akbar granted financial assistance and endowments to people from lower classes, rebels, and Hindus. After 1580, the number of non-Muslim beneficiaries of these grants increased significantly, including Hindus, Parsis, and Jains, who were provided with tax-free land endowments. Additionally, Jesuit priests were granted land for constructing churches. Outside Fatehpur Sikri, Akbar established two food distribution centers—"Dharmapura" for Hindus and "Khairpura" for Muslims. Later, as a large number of Jogis (ascetics) began arriving, he founded a third center called "Jogipura." Historians differ in their views regarding the extent to which Akbar was influenced by Hindu, Jain, Parsi, and Christian ideologies. However, it is evident that his religious policies promoted tolerance and harmony among various communities.*

Abu'l Fazl writes that representatives of various sects gathered for religious discussions, including Sufis, philosophers, judges, Sunnis, Shias, Brahmins, Jatis, Siurs, Charvaks, Nazarenes, Jews, Sabis, Parsis, and followers of other faiths, who found great pleasure in these debates. Here, the term "Jati" refers to followers of the Jain tradition, while "Siur" specifically indicates the Śvētāmbara Jains. In this context, it is relevant to mention Bada'uni, who wrote that—"In addition, Samanis and Brahmins often had the opportunity to converse with the emperor (Akbar) in private." The term "Samani" here refers to a worshiper or monk, specifically indicating Jain monks, who were often called "Yati."*Bada'uni states that Akbar was deeply influenced by Hinduism. He engaged in extensive discussions with renowned Hindu scholars like Purushottam and Devi Pandit. Akbar adopted several Hindu religious practices, such as worshipping fire and the sun, chanting the thousand names of the sun in Sanskrit, applying a tilak on his forehead, and observing the Rakhi tradition. Akbar firmly believed that truth exists in all religions, but blind imitation (taqlid) and excessive emphasis on religious rituals obscure this truth. Therefore, he did not adhere strictly to the doctrines of any single faith but rather held deep respect for all religions.***His reverence for fire is linked to the influence of Zoroastrianism. Due to the impact of Jainism, Akbar imposed a ban on animal slaughter on specific days. He prohibited cow slaughter and celebrated both Dussehra (a major Hindu festival) and Nowruz (the principal festival of Parsis). In Ain-i-Akbari, Abu'l Fazl noted Akbar's strong belief: "It is my duty to maintain harmony and reconciliation among all religions."Due to Akbar's assimilation of diverse religious beliefs, orthodox mullahs denounced his views as bid'ah (heretical innovations). Bada'uni accused him of disregarding Shari'ah (Islamic law) and claimed that there was no trace of Islam left in his heart. Similarly, the Christian missionary Father Monserrate remarked: "No one knows which religious code he follows. However, from his conduct, it is evident that he is not a Muslim."***Under the influence of Hindu scholars, Akbar became a supporter of the doctrine of rebirth. Through his interactions with various yogis, he learned yogic practices. He actively participated in the Shivaratri celebrations, using the occasion to gather yogis from near and far. Akbar would listen to their discourses on their beliefs and practices. Jahangir, in his book Tuzuk-e-Jahangiri, wrote: "Initially, Akbar adopted the customs of Hindustan in the same manner one enjoys the fresh fruits of a foreign land or the novel adornments of a new country—just as everything beloved appears delightful."

Akbar enthusiastically celebrated major Hindu festivals such as Diwali, Holi, and Raksha Bandhan. After the death of his mother, Hamida Banu, in 1604 CE, he performed the mundan (head-shaving) ritual as per Hindu tradition. He repeated the same ritual after the demise of the mother of his foster brother, Khan-e-Azam Mirza Aziz Koka, and Khan-e-Azam himself followed this tradition as well. Moreover, Hindus held Akbar in high esteem, and his glory was acknowledged in various texts.*Several historical records attest to Akbar's devotion and respect for Jainism. In a letter written from Lahore in 1595 CE, Portuguese priest Pinheiro mentioned that Akbar adhered to the principles of the Jain sect (Vetoi). Abul Fazl, in his list of prominent scholars during Akbar's reign, included several Jain saints, such as Hariji Suri, Vijayasen Suri, Bhānuchandra, Hiravijay Suri, Vijayasen Suri, and Bhānuchandra Upādhyāya. Sanskrit inscriptions also reference Hiravijay Suri, who deeply influenced Akbar after their interactions. The 1582–83 CE inscription at the Palitana temple indicates that Hiravijay Suri urged Akbar to implement several social and religious reforms, including:

A six-month ban on animal slaughter. The release of numerous prisoners and captive animals. The transfer of the sacred site Shatrunjaya to the Jain community.

Establishing a library for the preservation of Jain scriptures.

Abolishing the practice of confiscating the property of deceased individuals.

Promoting the construction of Jain temples in Gujarat and other regions.

Encouraging the expansion of Jainism in various territories.

Inspiring Akbar to undertake a pilgrimage to Shatrunjaya, following the ideals of King Shrenik.

Hiravijay Suri's disciple, Bhānuchandra, remained associated with Akbar's court until the later years of his reign. He composed a Sanskrit text titled Sūryasahasranāma, which contained interpretations of a thousand names of the Sun. After explaining the significance of these names to Akbar, the emperor introduced the practice of reciting them daily in his court. On one occasion, when Bhānuchandra arrived late to the court, Akbar inquired about the delay. The saint explained that his residence was far from the court, which caused the lateness. In response, Akbar donated land within Lahore Fort to the Jain community. A grand Jain temple was later constructed on this site, housing an

idol of tīrthānkara Shantinath and providing special accommodations for Jain saints.**Contemporary accounts from Bada'uni and Jesuit priests indicate that after 1581, Akbar no longer considered himself a Muslim. Ahmad Sirhindi strongly asserted that Akbar's tolerance towards non-Muslims was evidence of his hostility toward Islam. These accounts are crucial in understanding Akbar's policy of religious tolerance, as they provide clear insights into his beliefs and ideological stance.*** Akbar made significant efforts to ensure public peace, order, and justice within his empire. He sought to provide opportunities for his subjects to develop understanding and respect for different religions. To achieve this, Akbar established a special department dedicated to translating religious and scientific texts from Sanskrit, Arabic, Greek, and other languages into Persian. A group of scholars, including Hindu pandits, Jain scholars, Muslim intellectuals, and Zoroastrian priests, was assembled for this task. Among the translated works were major Hindu scriptures such as the Atharvaveda, Mahabharata, Ramayana, and Bhagavad Gita. According to Abul Fazl, Hindu and Muslim religious leaders were largely unfamiliar with each other's sacred texts. The primary objective of these translations was to foster mutual understanding and harmony between the two communities.*To understand the significance of India for Akbar and his followers, it is essential to examine the views of Abul Fazl. Expressing his patriotism, Abul Fazl describes the characteristics of the people of Hindustan: "The people of this land are God-fearing, generous, hospitable to strangers, blessed with beautiful faces and broad foreheads, protectors of knowledge and wisdom, lovers of asceticism, just, content, hardworking, skillful, loyal, perceptive of truth, and steadfast in their fidelity.*** Siddhichandra, in his biography of his guru Bhānuchandra Upādhyāya, writes about Akbar: "There is no art, no branch of knowledge and science, no act of courage and strength that the young Akbar has not mastered." He compared Akbar to Lord Rama, the son of Kaushalya, and claimed that under his reign, thieves and dacoits had completely disappeared. Siddhichandra further likened Akbar's greatness to the brilliance of the moon, as he had vanquished all his enemies. Additionally, he highlighted Akbar's religious tolerance: "Akbar's religious fervor never made him intolerant. His impartiality towards all six philosophical traditions is evident."***

Like his father Akbar, Jahangir also adopted the policy of Sulh-e-Kul (universal peace) and treated all religions with equality. Praising his father's religious tolerance, Jahangir writes: "In the vast expanse of his boundless dominion, there was space for followers of all religions. This was different from the customs of other states—for in Persia, only Shi'as are accommodated, and in Turkey, Hindustan, and Turan, space is given only to Sunnis." He further elaborates: "Within his empire, which was surrounded on all sides by the sea, there was room for adherents of opposing religions and beliefs, for both the virtuous and the wicked. The path of conflict was closed. Sunnis and Shi'as gathered in the same mosque, Europeans (Firangis) and Jews assembled in the same church and worshipped according to their respective religious traditions." Following the same principle of Sulh-e-Kul, Jahangir maintained religious tolerance throughout his reign.****During his reign, Jahangir continued the tradition of celebrating various Hindu festivals such as Diwali, Holi, Dussehra, Raksha Bandhan, and Shivratri as part of court festivities. Taking into account the faith of the Hindu community, public holidays were declared on these special occasions. Not only did Jahangir grant an honorable position to Hindu astrologers in his court, but he also had faith in their predictions. Additionally, he invited several Brahmin scholars to his court. This policy of Jahangir reflects that, like his father Akbar, he had a deep interest in and respect for Hindu religion and culture.***** Jahangir imposed a ban on cow slaughter in Punjab and extended this rule to Gujarat as well. Like Hindus, Christians were also granted full freedom to celebrate their festivals, such as Easter and Christmas. These traditions were a testament to his declaration of religious freedom for all. This policy facilitated social harmony among followers of different faiths and brought diverse cultures closer to each other. In the Tuzuk-e-Jahangiri, Jahangir emphasizes his commitment to religious freedom, stating: "I have ordered that, except for the practice of forced Sati, Hindus may follow all their prescribed customs, and no one should resort to coercion, force, or oppression against others." There were no restrictions on the construction of new Hindu temples during Jahangir's reign. In Mathura, Sher Singh Bundela built a grand temple, while several temples were also constructed in Banaras. Christians were granted land and assistance for building churches. Like his father Akbar, Jahangir continued the tradition of gifting and donating to temples. In the first year of his reign, he donated large sums of money to Brahmins and fakirs. Documents related to the temples associated with the Chaitanya sect in Vrindavan reveal that Jahangir consistently provided grants to temples and their devotees. Between 1612 and 1615, he issued at least five grants to the Chaitanya sect in Vrindavan.

In 1621, when Jahangir passed through Haridwar, he wrote: "This is a revered place of worship for Hindus, where Brahmins and ascetics retreat to beautiful locations and engage in their respective modes of worship." He granted many of these individuals monetary rewards and land grants. In Ajmer, Jahangir donated the entire village of Pushkar to the local Brahmins as maa'ash (a livelihood grant) to support them.*

Jahangir found the greatest peace and tranquility in the company of Vedanta followers. He regarded Vedanta and Tasawwuf (Sufism) as fundamentally similar. In 1616, he met the saint Jagat Gosain in Ujjain and visited him seven times over the next three years. Hearing of the renowned ascetic Jadrup, Jahangir wished to invite him to Agra. However, to ensure that the saint faced no inconvenience, Jahangir himself walked a distance of one to two furlongs to meet him. Deeply impressed by Jadrup's wisdom and simplicity, Jahangir stated that the saint had attained complete mastery over Vedanta. When Jadrup later moved to Mathura, Jahangir visited him there twice. At that time, Hakim Beg, the governor of Mathura and the brother-in-law of Nur Jahan, mistreated Jadrup. Enraged by this incident, Jahangir immediately dismissed Hakim Beg from his position.** This incident illustrates the deep respect Jahangir had for Hinduism and his adherence to the Sulh-e-Kul (universal peace) policy, following in the footsteps of his father, Akbar. After Jahangir, Shah Jahan ascended the throne. While he introduced some external changes, he continued Akbar's policy of Sulh-e-Kul. Shah Jahan had a profound affection for his eldest son, Dara Shikoh, who significantly influenced his worldview. Dara Shikoh's personality was defined by his broad religious perspective, humanitarian outlook, and commitment to fostering harmony among diverse communities. Drawing inspiration from Emperor Akbar's policies, he actively promoted love and goodwill between the followers of Hinduism and Islam. Throughout his life, he worked toward strengthening Hindu-Muslim unity. Dara Shikoh firmly believed that dividing humanity based on religion or social status was unjust. He held that all human beings were equal and that every religion ultimately led to the same universal truth.*** Shah Jahan was influenced by Dara Shikoh's liberal views, which were reflected in his policies of religious tolerance and harmony. In 1629, Shah Jahan granted land to Shantidas, a Jain merchant and The policy of religious tolerance continued during Shah Jahan's reign. This is evident from the fact that he confirmed the grants previously given to Vaishnav temples in Vrindavan. More significantly, he allowed the installation of time-indicating bells (ghariyal) in temples, symbolizing the continuation of Akbar's Sulh-e-Kul policy.

On November 10, 1635, Shah Jahan, through an official decree bearing the seal of Nawab Bardasht Khan, granted a tax-free jagir to Mohan Bhatt in Baliya village for the protection and promotion of Hinduism.* Similarly, in February 1632, Radha Rai, a resident of Srinagar village, Pargana Haveli Tajpur, Purnia district, was granted 200 bighas of tax-free land for the preservation and advancement of Hindu religious traditions.** Meanwhile, Sheikh Abdul Haq and Sheikh Ahmad Sirhindi attempted to expand their influence. To gain the support of some influential courtiers, they put forward certain demands, which historian Satish Chandra documents:

1. Humiliation of Hindus: This included the destruction of temples, discouraging social interactions with Hindus, denying them government jobs, and, if hiring them was necessary, ensuring they were not given any position of trust or responsibility.

2. Reimposition of the Jizya tax.

3. Elimination of Bid'ah (innovations): This referred to the removal of all practices deemed un-Islamic under Sharia, including cultural traditions (such as music and painting), moral behaviors (such as alcohol consumption), and social customs (such as Tuladan and Jharokha Darshan).

Like Jahangir, Shah Jahan rejected these demands, demonstrating that he maintained a balanced approach and did not disregard or reject any of Akbar's liberal policies.*** After Shah Jahan, the reign of Aurangzeb began. It is important to note that Aurangzeb's religious policy should not be judged solely based on his personal religious beliefs. Regarding Aurangzeb's religious outlook, historian Satish Chandra makes a noteworthy observation: "He refused to dismiss Hindu kings and other non-Muslim officials from government positions. In response to such a request, he firmly replied, 'What does religion have to do with worldly affairs, and what is the point of associating religious practices with fanaticism? For you is your religion, and for me is mine. If (the rule you suggest) were to be implemented, it would become my duty to eliminate all Hindu kings and their followers.'" ****

The destruction of temples by Aurangzeb was not driven by religious motives but rather by political considerations. British historians reinforced the notion that he demolished temples out of hatred for Hinduism. However, this idea was propagated during the colonial era by British historians, whose primary objective was to create hostility between Hindu and Muslim communities. Their ultimate aim was to divide Indian society, seize control of its resources, and establish a firm and lasting rule over India.

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In 1654, Aurangzeb issued a royal decree to Mewar's Rajput ruler, Rana Raj Singh, clarifying the appropriate conduct that good rulers should maintain towards temples and religious sites of other faiths. "Since the personality of great emperors is a reflection of God's shadow, it is the duty of this noble class, which serves as the pillars of the Divine Court, to ensure that people of different dispositions and religions (mazahib) live in an atmosphere of peace and spend their days in prosperity, without any interference in each other's affairs." Aurangzeb's core message was that a king is God's representative, and therefore, it is his duty to establish peace and equality among different religious communities. According to Aurangzeb, Mughal traditions and Islamic teachings had taught him to protect pilgrimage sites, Hindu temples, and holy men.*

Between 1948 and 1953, when B. N. Pandey was the chairman of Allahabad (now Prayagraj) Municipality, a land dispute was brought before him. The land in question had been gifted to the Someshwarnath Mahadev Temple. After the death of the temple's Mahant (head priest), two parties claimed ownership over it. One of the parties presented historical documents that contained references to royal orders issued by Aurangzeb. These records clearly indicated that Aurangzeb had granted the temple a significant land endowment and financial assistance, with a condition that the income generated from it must be used exclusively for temple rituals and other religious activities. Additionally, at Ujjain's Mahakaleshwar Temple, there was a tradition of keeping a sacred lamp (Akhanda Deep) burning 24/7. Some of Aurangzeb's local officials attempted to discontinue this practice. In protest, the temple priests submitted a petition to Aurangzeb. In response, Aurangzeb ordered his official, Muhammad Mehndi, to investigate the matter. After conducting an inquiry, Aurangzeb issued a decree stating that the temple should receive four seers of ghee daily from the local Kotwali (revenue officer) to ensure the continuous burning of the sacred lamp.** Before Aurangzeb's arrival in Brahmपुरi, South India, an official named Mir Hasan wrote a letter stating: "The fort of Islampur has weakened, and since your arrival is imminent, its repairs are necessary. Kindly issue your instructions regarding this matter." Aurangzeb responded: "You have erred by calling it 'Islampur.' The actual name of this place is Brahmपुरi, and you should use this name only."

According to records preserved in a Hyderabad museum, an incident of religious significance occurred when Aurangzeb was stationed in the Deccan to suppress revolts. During his stay, a Shiva Lingam idol was stolen from the house of a Brahmin family in a nearby village. Suspicion fell upon a Muslim family from the same village. The affected Brahmin, who would not eat or drink without offering prayers to the Shiva Lingam, reached a critical condition nearing death. His wife informed Aurangzeb about the matter. Upon hearing this, Aurangzeb immediately ordered his officials: "Find the idol within a day, or the entire village will be punished." Historical records confirm that the stolen idol was successfully recovered and restored to the Brahmin family.*

Aurangzeb's statement, in which he asserted that Mughal tradition and Islamic teachings had instructed him to protect pilgrimage sites, Hindu temples, and revered figures, is corroborated by Audrey Truschke's account-" In one of his early acts as emperor, Aurangzeb issued an imperial order (farman) to local Mughal officials at Benares that directed them to halt any interference in the affairs of local temples. Writing in February of 1659 Aurangzeb said he had learned that 'several people have, out of spite and rancour, harassed the Hindu residents of Benares and nearby places, including a group of Brahmins who are in charge of ancient temples there'.The king then ordered his officials: 'You must see that nobody unlawfully disturbs the Brahmins or other Hindus of that region, so that they might remain in their traditional place and pray for the continuance of the Empire.' The ending of the 1659 Benares farman became a common refrain in the many imperial commands penned by Aurangzeb that protected temples and their caretakers: they should be left alone so that Brahmins could pray for the longevity of the Mughal state. In the ninth year of his reign Aurangzeb dispensed a farman to the Umanand Temple at Guwahati in Assam, confirming an earlier land grant and the associated right to collect revenue. In 1680 he directed that Bhagwant Gosain, a Hindu ascetic who lived on the banks of the Ganges in Benares, should be kept free from harassment. In 1687, the emperor gave some empty land on a ghat in Benares (which was, incidentally, near a mosque) to Ramjivan Gosain in order to build houses for 'pious Brahmins and holy faqirs'. In 1691 Aurangzeb conferred eight villages and a sizable chunk of tax-free land on Mahant Balak Das Nirvani of Chitrakoot to support the Balaji Temple. In 1698 he gifted rent-free land to a Brahmin named Rang Bhatt, son of Nek

Bhatt, in eastern Khandesh in central India. The list goes on and includes temples and individuals in Allahabad, Vrindavan, Bihar, and elsewhere.

Aurangzeb carried on the traditions of his forefathers in granting favours to Hindu religious communities, a continuity underscored by his dealings with the Jangam, a Shaivite group. The Jangam benefited from Mughal orders beginning under Akbar, who confirmed their legal rights to land in 1564. The same Jangam received several farmans from Aurangzeb that restored land that had been unfairly confiscated (1667), protected them from a disruptive local Muslim (1672), and returned illegally charged rent (1674). Such measures ensured that pious individuals could continue their religious activities, a component of Aurangzeb's vision of justice.

Aurangzeb enacted similarly favourable policies towards Jain religious institutions. Again following Akbar's example, Aurangzeb granted land at Shatrunjaya, Girnar, and Mount Abu—all Jain pilgrimage destinations in Gujarat—to specific Jain communities in the late 1650s. He gave Lal Vijay, a Jain monk, a monastery (poshala), probably sometime before 1681, and granted relief for a resting house (upashraya) in 1679. As late as 1703,

Aurangzeb issued orders prohibiting people from harassing Jina Chandra Suri, a Jain religious leader. Given such actions, it is unsurprising that we find laudatory descriptions of the emperor in vernacular Jain works of this period, such as, 'Aurangzeb Shah is a brave and powerful king' (mardano aur

mahabali aurangasahi naranda).^{*} Aurangzeb's primary objective was to ensure the smooth administration of his empire, and he did not even spare mosques if they obstructed his governance policies. For instance, when the ruler of Golconda failed to pay tribute to Aurangzeb for three consecutive years, the Mughal emperor gathered intelligence through his spies and discovered that the Nawab had hidden his wealth in the basement of a mosque. Consequently, Aurangzeb ordered the demolition of the mosque to retrieve the treasure and have it sent to Delhi. This raises an important question: Can Aurangzeb be considered an ideal Muslim ruler based on such actions, as some attempts are made to portray him today? On the contrary, in Vrindavan (Varanasi), Aurangzeb donated gold ornaments to a Krishna temple. Even today, the idol of Lord Krishna in this temple is adorned with the same ornaments gifted by Aurangzeb.^{**}

Conclusion

Thus, we can clearly see that when the Mughals came to India, they gradually shed their foreign identity and became truly Indian in every sense, as evident from their conduct. The Mughal era laid the foundation for a shared cultural heritage that deeply influenced India's secular and multicultural identity.

Later, British historians sought to strengthen their rule in India by sidelining the Mughals' religious inclusivity and portraying them solely as Islamic rulers. Among these British historians, Sir Henry M. Elliot played a prominent role. In 1849, Sir Henry M. Elliot, along with his assistant John Dowson, compiled the eight-volume "History of India as Told by Its Own Historians." Elliot's primary objective was to depict the British as just rulers while portraying Muslims as cruel and oppressive.

The impact of his distorted historical narrative on future generations' perception of medieval Indian history has been profoundly damaging. Reflecting on this, historian Mohammad Habib once remarked: "The peace-loving Indian Muslim, who undoubtedly descended from Hindu ancestors, was portrayed as a foreign barbarian—a temple destroyer, a beef-eater, and a military colonizer who was labeled an outsider in the very land where he had lived for the past thirty to forty centuries. The consequences of this misrepresentation can be seen in the communal atmosphere of India today."^{**}

The impact of the British misinterpretation of history can still be observed today. The

current situation is such that the 190-year rule of the British, during which they enslaved Indians, exploited India in every possible way, and looted its wealth to send to England, is often overlooked. In contrast, the Mughals are portrayed as the primary enemies of India, which is not the truth. This is a direct consequence of the historical misrepresentation by the British.

In the present time, it has become essential to deeply analyze subjects related to religion and history, as these are the aspects that influence human thoughts and emotions. To view Ram and Muhammad with the same perspective, a person must possess extensive religious knowledge and a mature mindset. It is necessary not only to show respect for each other's beliefs but also to make an effort to understand them. Historical and religious studies can play a crucial role in fostering this awareness. The way Hindus and Muslims perceive history in India has always been different, whether in the past or the present. Generally, a Hindu hesitates to consider a Muslim ruler or historical figure as their ancestor, and similarly, a Muslim is reluctant to acknowledge a Hindu historical figure as their ancestor. If both communities develop the ability to view history with an impartial perspective and learn to coexist with mutual love and harmony, then the problem of Hindu-Muslim conflicts might never arise. If history were studied objectively and with understanding, and religious teachings were interpreted correctly, positive outcomes would emerge. Hindus and Muslims would become so outwardly similar that distinguishing between them would be difficult, and feelings of love and respect for one another would naturally develop in their hearts. In reality, an individual's mental perspective is what gives rise to peace and unity in society, but it is also what leads to misunderstandings and conflicts. Therefore, by developing a correct understanding of history and religion, social harmony can be strengthened.**

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